

CHARACTERIZATION OF FLEXIBLE TOWPREGS FOR TEXTILE PROCESSING

A. Ramasamy and Y. Wang
School of Textile & Fiber Engineering
and
J. Muzzy
School of Chemical Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, GA 30332

ABSTRACT

Textile preforms offer the potential for producing low cost, complex shaped, advanced composite structures. For thermoplastic composites in particular it is advantageous to incorporate the resin in the tow prior to textile processing since it is difficult to impregnate dry fabrics with thermoplastic melts. Flexible towpreg is made by powder fusion coating without consolidation. In this paper the characterization and braiding of flexible nylon 6/carbon fiber towpregs is emphasized. The debulking of the resulting braids and the compression molding of a braided composite are described. Wrapping the towpreg with nylon 6 filaments improved braiding significantly. A well consolidated laminate was obtained using a peak time, temperature and pressure cycle of 5 minutes, 260°C and 700 kPa.

KEYWORDS: Preforms, Braids, Towpregs, Thermoplastics, Consolidation

1. INTRODUCTION

Textile preforming methods are increasingly recognized in recent years as an important component in composite manufacturing systems. Composites from textile preforms are shown to have superior damage tolerance and processibility when compared to other methods of composite manufacturing (1). Towpregs are continuous filament tows coated with matrix forming polymers. Compared to wet lay up, composites from towpregs offer consistency in mechanical properties, controlled resin content, and uniform distribution of resin and fiber(2). However, towpregs with solid matrices are generally too stiff to be easily processed through a textile preforming operation. In order to realize the advantages of textile preforms when using towpregs with solidified matrices there is a need to make the towpregs very flexible. Towpregs produced by commingling and powder fusion coating have demonstrated good flexibility(3,4). Although commingled tows are quite flexible, it is necessary to use more intensive processing conditions to consolidate commingled preforms since there is no wetout of the reinforcing fiber. Furthermore, this approach is limited by the need to convert the matrix into fibers, which is an expensive and sometimes a difficult process. The focus of this work is to evaluate the towpregs produced by an electrostatic powder fusion coating process (4,5) for efficient composite manufacturing through textile preforming by braiding. The powder coated towpregs are characterized for friction and bending properties which are critical in textile processing. Then, these towpregs are converted into braids. The stress relaxation behavior and

cover factor of these braids are reported. Then the debulking and consolidation of one braid is described.

2. MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

Carbon fiber tow: Unsized 12K Celion G30-500 carbon fiber from BASF and TOHO.

Towpregs: The above tow is coated with nylon 6 (Allied Signal) and polypropylene (Aristech) powders using the electrostatic powder fusion coating system at Custom Composite Materials Inc. The percentage of powder in the towpreg is maintained between 30 and 35% by weight.

Braiding: Braiding is carried out using a 72 carrier Wardwell composite braiding machine. This machine has 48 braiding carriers and 24 axial carriers housed on a platform. This platform can be set to move at the required traverse rate. The support for the mandrel is attached to the machine frame which does not move. The braiding speed and the traverse rate of the platform can be changed continuously. The braiding rate can be varied up to a speed of 360 picks/minute. The braid angle can be changed between 5° to 85° depending upon the material being braided. The braider is equipped with a braiding ring of 152.4 mm diameter. The braiding carriers are fitted with wheels, instead of fixed guides, to reduce the frictional resistance.

Braiding Procedure: For all the experiments, flat braids are made by braiding a tubular braid first and cutting them along the length. The diameter of the tubular mandrel is selected using the following equation as a guide:

$$D_f = (N_b W_b / 2 \cos(\theta) + N_a W_a) / \pi \quad (1)$$

where D_f = diameter of the tube (mm)

N_b = number of braider yarns

N_a = number of axial yarns

W_b = width of the braider yarn (mm)

W_a = width of the axial yarn (mm)

θ = braid angle

The width of the towpregs are measured by wrapping the towpreg around a tube. During braiding the width of the towpreg changes depending upon the braiding tension and the friction between the towpregs when they cross each other. The braid angle also changes due to increased frictional resistance between the towpregs. This makes it difficult for the towpregs to pack close to each other. Due to these problems it is difficult to obtain preforms with 100% cover factor. Cover factor is defined as the ratio of the projected area of the towpregs to that of the preform. Other problems with braiding the towpregs are splitting of the towpregs into many segments, tangling between neighboring towpregs, and towpregs jumping off of the wheels of the braiding carriers.

Wrapping: To avoid the above problems, the towpregs are wrapped with 200 Denier nylon 6 filaments in a back winding operation. Back winding is used to prepare bobbins for braiding from the supplier's bobbins. To wrap during back winding, the towpregs are made to run through the hollow spindle carrying the wrapping filaments, while this spindle rotates and wraps the filament around towpregs. The number of wraps per unit length of the towpreg can be changed by either changing the rotational speed of hollow spindle or by changing the speed at which the towpreg moves, which is affected by changing the take up package speed. Braiding is carried out with towpregs wrapped with nylon 6 filaments at 0.06 wraps/mm.

3. FRICTION OF TOWPREGS

Although fiber frictional behavior has been studied over the past several decades(6-10), its nature in fibers remains complex and is largely unknown. There are many theories proposed in the past to explain the frictional behavior between two bodies. The classical theory is based on Amonton's-

Coulombs' equation(6). According to this theory, the maximum frictional force (F) is directly proportional to the normal force (N),

$$F = \mu N \tag{2}$$

where μ is the coefficient of friction. According to this equation, μ is a material property, independent of area of contact and the normal force. For the case of a thread moving around a fixed cylinder, the following equation relates the impeding force (T_1) and the driving force (T_2)

$$T_2 = T_1 e^{\mu\theta} \tag{3}$$

where θ is the wrap angle.

3. 1. Experimental Procedures: Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the apparatus used to study the frictional behavior of towpregs. In this setup, to one end of a towpreg, a known weight (T_1) is attached and the other end of the towpreg is passed around a frictionless pulley, a steel rod (diameter = 12.7 mm) covered with towpregs, and then is attached to the load cell of an Instron tensile testing machine. To cover the steel rod with towpregs, towpregs are laid parallel to the length of the rod and they are tied with a string tightly to the steel rod. For each test, a fresh region on this rod and new towpreg are used so that the damage done to towpreg in one test does not affect the results of the next test. The cross head of the tensile tester is moved at a specified speed and the load-displacement curve is obtained. Equation 3 is used to calculate the coefficient of friction.

FIGURE 1. (a) Set up for Friction Measurement and (b) Typical Load- Displacement Curve.

3.2. Results and Discussion: Typical load-displacement curves obtained from friction tests on carbon tows and towpregs are shown in Figure 1b. In the case of towpregs, there is considerable fluctuation in the instantaneous load. The static coefficient of friction (μ_s) is calculated based on the initial load (T_o). Results for different matrices are presented in Table 1. The powder coating

increases the coefficient of friction significantly. For nylon 6 the friction is almost twice the uncoated tow. Nylon 11 and polypropylene have lower friction coefficients whereas PEEK is higher. These coefficients are sensitive to particle size and coating conditions as well as the type of matrix. Since it is beneficial to wrap the towpreg for braiding, the effect of extent of wrapping on the coefficient of friction was studied. As shown in Table 2, increased wrapping leads to a modest decline in the coefficient of friction. This decline is beneficial; but, it is not enough to explain the much greater ease of braiding wrapped towpreg.

TABLE 1. COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION OF TOWPREGS WITH DIFFERENT MATRIX MATERIALS.

Materials	μ_s (CV)
Hercules 6K AS 4 uncoated carbon tow	0.21 (0.04)
Hercules 12K AS4 carbon fiber/ Allied Signal Nylon 6	0.43 (0.13)
BASF 12K G30-500/Nylon 6 + 0.38 Wraps/mm fiber	0.41 (0.09)
Hercules 6K AS4 carbon fiber/ Atochem nylon11	0.31 (0.10)
BASF 12K G30-500 carbon fiber/Aristech Polypropylene	0.30 (0.09)
Hercules 12K AS4 carbon fiber/ ICI PEEK 150 PF	0.52 (0.12)

The fixed parameters for these tests are: 254 mm/minute. cross head speed, 180° wrap angle and 0.98N impeding force (T_j).

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF WRAP DENSITY ON COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION AND BENDING RIGIDITY OF NYLON 6 TOWPREGS.

No. of Wraps/mm	Coefficient of Friction		Bending Rigidity	
	μ	CV	(10^{-8} Nm ²)	CV
0	0.43	(0.13)	142	(0.15)
0.04	0.41	(0.09)	140	(0.24)
0.06	0.38	(0.06)	148	(0.22)
0.08	0.40	(0.15)	164	(0.19)
0.16	0.34	(0.17)	179	(0.26)
0.24	0.36	(0.08)	182	(0.22)

4. FLEXIBILITY OF TOWPREGS

4.1 Experimental Procedures: Towpreg flexibility has been characterized using two methods: cantilever bending and pure bending (in a Kawabata Evaluation System). For cantilever bending, the overhang length is measured for a deflection of 25.4 mm and the bending rigidity, EI is calculated using the formula for a self-weighted cantilever beam:

$$EI = PL^4/8\delta \tag{4}$$

where, P is the weight per unit length of the material, L is the overhang length and δ is the deflection (25.4 mm). The typical bending curvature in this test ranges from 0.3×10^{-3} to 3.0×10^{-3} mm⁻¹. This curvature is much lower than the bending encountered in processing. Therefore pure bending testing with greater curvature is explored.

The pure bending testing is carried out using a Kawabata Evaluation System (KES). The KES was developed to evaluate the hand properties of textile fabrics. In this system, a specimen of 10 mm length is subjected to pure bending between two grips. One grip stays stationary at 'o' and the other grip moves along the curve given by the equations in Figure 2. The specimen is bent between

curvatures $+0.25$ and -0.25 mm^{-1} . The instrument calculates the mean of the slope of the bending moment versus curvature which is bending rigidity, in two ranges of curvature values: $+0.05$ to $+0.15 \text{ mm}^{-1}$ and -0.05 to -0.15 mm^{-1} . The average of these two values is taken as the bending rigidity.

FIGURE 2. Bending of Towpreg in the Kawabata Evaluation System.

4.2. Results and Discussion: Bending rigidity as a function of wraps per millimeter is reported in Table 2. There is a gradual increase in rigidity as the linear density of wraps increases. This trend is not desirable since flexible towpregs are easier to process due to the extensive curvatures encountered in braiding.

Bending rigidities for different systems are presented in Table 3. From Table 3, it is clear that the towpregs are much stiffer than the uncoated carbon tows of the same size. This again suggests problems like breaking of filaments when the towpregs pass around high curvature since a textile process usually involves bending of threads around sharp curvature. In cantilever bending tests, the bending rigidity values are measured at low bending curvatures (0.3×10^{-3} to $3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^{-1}$.) whereas in the KES pure bending tests these values are measured at very high curvatures ($+0.05$ to $+0.15 \text{ mm}^{-1}$). Consequently, the bending rigidity values obtained with cantilever bending tests are much higher than those obtained with the pure bending test. This indicates that the interfilament slippage increases with an increase in bending curvature, causing a decrease in bending rigidity. This also suggests that the bending rigidity should be measured at a curvature close to that involved in textile processing.

TABLE 3 . RESULTS OF BENDING TESTS ON TOWPREGS.

Material	Bending rigidity (10^{-8} Nm^2)	
	Cantilever bending (CV)	Pure bending (CV)
Hercules 3K AS4 uncoated carbon tow.		0.4 (0.11)
Hercules 6K AS4 uncoated carbon tow.		0.6 (0.09)
Hercules 12K AS4 carbon fiber/ Allied Signal nylon-6	364.2 (0.25)	13.9 (0.18)
Hercules 6K AS4 carbon fiber/ Atochem nylon-11	404.7 (0.32)	20.1 (0.25)
BASF 12K Celion G30-500/ Aristech Polypropylene	341.6 (0.22)	12.8 (0.18)
Hercules 12K AS4 carbon fiber/ ICI PEEK 150 PF	522.1 (0.23)	19.5 (0.21)

5. BRAIDING STUDIES

In braiding trials carried out with unwrapped towpregs problems with towpreg breaking and towpreg entanglement were encountered. Also the preform obtained is not uniform due to excessive fiber damage and improper converging. Furthermore, the preform is quite bulky. Picture (a) in Figure 4 shows a typical appearance of a preform made in this trial (*NT60*). All further braiding is carried out with towpregs wrapped with nylon 6 filaments. Picture (b) in Figure 4 shows a typical appearance of a preform made in these trials. Table 4 summarizes the structures expected and obtained in these braiding trials.

TABLE 4. BRAIDED STRUCTURES EXPECTED AND OBTAINED

Code	Wrapping	Braid angle		Cover factor		Weight/area g/m ²
		Expected	Actual	Expected	Estimate*	
<i>NT60</i>	No	60	63	100	96	397.3
<i>WBO45</i>	Yes	45	49	85	82	479.0
<i>WBC45</i>	Yes	45	42	100	93	668.3
<i>WBO60</i>	Yes	60	54	85	79	460.8
<i>WTC60</i>	Yes	45	58	100	91	655.8

* Calculated by counting the number of towpregs per unit length and measuring the width of the towpreg.

The above braids are part of a set of experiments to study the effect of braid angle, cover factor and braid pattern on the properties of preforms which are important in the molding performance of preforms. While molding parts with complicated shapes, the preform needs to follow the contours of the mold as closely as possible to reduce the possible waviness in the parts at sharp bends. This problem is similar to the "hand" of textile fabrics. The hand of a fabric is the ability to follow any curvature smoothly. The Kawabata Evaluation System (KES) is a popular and sensitive system developed to evaluate the hand of fabrics. In this system, tensile, compressive, shear, bending and

FIGURE 4. Photographs of Braids Produced in the Braiding Trials.
 (a) Braid with out Wrapping Filaments (*NT60*).
 (b) Braid with Wrapping Filaments (*WBC45*).

surface properties of a fabric are measured at low stress levels (e.g. compression testing is done at 500 kPa) and a data base is developed for different types of fabrics. These values are then compared with rankings of experts to establish standards. In the case of composite preforms, the values obtained through the KES tests can be standardized with different molding experiments. Since the composite preforms are quite different from the traditional textile preforms, some of the properties of the preforms fall outside the range of the KES equipment. For example, high performance fiber preforms are usually stiffer than apparel fabrics. From some trial tests carried out, it has been observed that the bending rigidity of these preforms are outside the range of the KES pure bending test equipment. So, the bending properties will be studied on a MTS testing machine. Moreover, in the case of composite molding, heat and pressure are applied. So, the behavior of preforms at different temperature and pressure should also be studied. The tests which are of particular importance for this application involves studying the stress relaxation and the creep behavior of the braided fiber mat assembly. This compressive creep is analogous to debulking or partial bulk consolidation. Debulking is usually carried out to reduce the bulkiness of the fiber assembly to fit a mold easily. This is done at a moderate temperature which is lower than the final consolidation temperature.

5.1. Stress Relaxation Test: As a part of series of tests to be done to study the stress relaxation behavior of preforms at different temperatures, a stress relaxation test is done on preform without wrapping filaments (NT60) at room temperature. This test is carried out using the MTS 810 testing machine. Four layers of the preform (101.6mm x 101.6mm) are stacked one on top of another and the thickness was noted when the preforms just start taking the load. Based on the densities of fiber and resin and the fiber volume fraction (55% obtained from the powder deposition process), the final composite thickness would be 1.09 mm assuming no voids in the composite. These four layers are compressed to 5.44 mm which is five times the final composite thickness and the cross head was kept at this gap for 3 minutes and the drop in the load was measured.

From the load Vs time plot, an instantaneous drop of 22% in the load has been observed and there is no further drop in the load over the period in which the test is carried out. This indicates that possibly permanent change occurred in the fiber assembly in the way the fibers are placed. The percentage drop in the load again indicates how compliant the fiber assembly is. Since the matrix material is a thermoplastic, it is reasonable to expect the stress relaxation behavior to change with different temperatures. But, this change will be accompanied by possible changes in the flexibility of the fiber assembly. By conducting tests at different temperatures and studying the reduction in the bulkiness and changes in the flexibility, it should be possible to find optimal conditions for debulking.

5.2. Consolidation experiment: In order to see the overall quality of the composites made from these braids, one of the above braids (WBO45) is consolidated and a C-Scan is taken for the laminate. Consolidation is done using a 50.8 mm x 292.1 mm mold. Two layers of the braids are heated to 260°C in the mold and at this temperature, the mold is closed for 5 minutes under a load of 700 kPa. The mold is cooled under the same pressure to room temperature. The density of the specimen is found to be 1.45 g/cm³ and the thickness is 0.76 mm. C-Scanning is carried out using an Ultracac II from Physical Acoustics Corporation. From the C-Scan, it appears that the ends of the specimen are not uniform since the mold used in this case is an open ended mold. But, away from these edges the sample appears to well consolidated.

6. SUMMARY

In order to combine the advantages of flexible towpregging technology and textile preforming processes, it is required to characterize the towpregs for the properties which are critical for textile processing. In this work test methods to test the friction and bending characteristics of towpregs produced by the electrostatic fusion coated towpregs have been developed. Carbon fiber towpregs with different matrix materials have been characterized for friction and bending properties. Results indicate that the towpregs have higher coefficient of friction and higher flexural rigidity values when compared to uncoated tows from which they are made. Braiding trials have been carried out with powder fusion coated towpregs. Wrapping of the nylon 6 coated towpregs with nylon 6 filaments improved the braiding performance of the towpregs to a considerable extent. A stress relaxation test

is conducted on one of the preforms at room temperature. A laminate consolidated with a powder coated preform is C-Scanned and it appears quite uniform.

7. FUTURE WORK

This characterization of flexible towpregs and 2D preforms derived from these towpregs is part of a research program to develop the processing science for manufacturing composites based on textile technologies. It is the intent of the authors to relate towpreg properties to textile processibility as well as preform characteristics. In turn, preform properties will be related to composite forming and consolidation behavior and product quality.

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